

Table 1: Primary studies

Id	Paper	Year	Author	Reference
PS1	Psychological Safety, Leadership and Non-Technical Debt in Large-Scale Agile Software Development.	2023	Ahmad, M. O.	[1]
PS2	“The Second Vice is Lying, the First is Running into Debt.” Antecedents and Mitigating Practices of Social Debt: An Exploratory Study in Distributed Software Development Teams”.	2021	Dreesen <i>et al.</i>	[2]
PS3	A Multivocal Literature Review on Non-Technical Debt in Software Development: An Insight into Process, Social, People, Organizational, and Culture Debt.	2024	Saeeda <i>et al.</i>	[3]
PS4	Software architecture social debt: Managing the incommunicability factor.	2019	D.A.Tamburri.	[4]
PS5	Splicing Community and Software Architecture Smells in Agile Teams: An industrial Study.	2019	Tamburri <i>et al.</i>	[5]
PS6	Exploring Community Smells in Open-Source: An Automated Approach.	2017	Tamburri <i>et al.</i>	[6]
PS7	Understanding community smells variability: A statistical approach.	2021	Catolino <i>et al.</i>	[7]
PS8	The architect’s role in community shepherding.	2016	Tamburri <i>et al.</i>	[8]
PS9	An Empirical Study of Social Debt in Open-Source Projects: Social Drivers and the “Known Devil” Community Smell.	2024	Chen <i>et al.</i>	[9]
PS10	Debt Stories: Capturing Social and Technical Debt in the Industry.	2024	Riquet <i>et al.</i>	[10]
PS11	Gender Diversity and Community Smells: A Double-Replication Study on Brazilian Software Teams.	2022	Sarmiento <i>et al.</i>	[11]
PS12	Effective Social Productivity Measurements During Software Development: An Empirical Study.	2016	Yilmaz <i>et al.</i>	[12]
PS13	Gender Diversity and Community Smells: Insights from the Trenches.	2020	Catolino <i>et al.</i>	[13]
PS14	Analyzing the Relationship between Community and Design Smells in Open-Source Software Projects: An Empirical Study.	2022	Haque <i>et al.</i>	[14]
PS15	Locating community smells in software development processes using higher-order network centralities.	2023	Gote <i>et al.</i>	[15]
PS16	Discovering community patterns in open-source: a systematic approach and its evaluation.	2019	Tamburri <i>et al.</i>	[16]
PS17	Measuring affective states from technical debt: A psychoempirical software engineering experiment.	2021	Olsson <i>et al.</i>	[17]
PS18	Community smell occurrence prediction on multi-granularity by developer-oriented features and process metrics.	2022	Huang <i>et al.</i>	[18]
PS19	The influence of Technical Debt on software developer morale.	2020	Besker <i>et al.</i>	[19]
PS20	Towards Understanding the Social and Organizational Dimensions of Software Architecting.	2017	Galster <i>et al.</i>	[20]

Id	Paper	Year	Author	Reference
PS21	Are we working well with others? How the multi team systems impact software quality.	2019	M. Lavallée <i>et al.</i> ,	[21]
PS22	Towards Power Relationship Dynamics and Community Smells in the Proprietary Software Ecosystem.	2023	B. B. Ribeiro <i>et al.</i>	[22]
PS23	In Search of Socio-Technical Congruence: A Large-Scale Longitudinal Study.	2022	Silveira <i>et al.</i>	[23]
PS24	Good Fences Make Good Neighbours? on the Impact of Cultural and Geographical Dispersion on Community Smells.	2022	M. T. Baldassarre <i>et al.</i>	[24]
PS25	The emotional side of software developers in JIRA.	2019	G. Destefanis <i>et al.</i>	[25]
PS26	A Preliminary Insights on Industry Practices for Addressing Fairness Debt.	2024	A. Shahriari <i>et al.</i>	[26]
PS27	Community smells-The sources of social debt: A systematic literature review.	2023	Caballero-Espinosa, J. C. Carver and K. Stowers.	[27]
PS28	Predicting the emergence of community smells using socio-technical metrics: A machine-learning approach.	2020	Palomba and Tamburri.	[28]
PS29	Impacts of software community patterns on process and product: An empirical study.	2021	De Stefano <i>et al.</i>	[29]
PS30	Improving the detection of community smells through socio-technical and sentiment analysis.	2023	Almarimi <i>et al.</i>	[30]
PS31	Learning to Detect Community Smells in Open Source Software Projects.	2020	Almarimi, Ouni, and Mkaouer.	[31]
PS32	Refactoring Community Smells: An Empirical Study on the Software Practitioners of Bangladesh.	2022	G. Catolino <i>et al.</i>	[32]
PS33	Refactoring Community Smells in the Wild: The Practitioner’s Field Manual.	2020	G. Catolino <i>et al.</i>	[33]
PS34	On the Detection of Community Smells Using Genetic Programming-based Ensemble Classifier Chain.	2020	Almarimi <i>et al.</i>	[34]
PS35	Splicing Community Patterns and Smells: A Preliminary Study.	2020	De Stefano <i>et al.</i>	[35]
PS36	Predicting Community Smells’ Occurrence on Individual Developers by Sentiments.	2021	Z. Huang <i>et al.</i>	[36]
PS37	An empirical study on the effect of community smells on bug prediction.	2021	Eken <i>et al.</i>	[37]
PS38	Understanding the Relationship between Missing Link Community Smell and Fix-inducing Changes.	2021	Ahammed <i>et al.</i>	[38]
PS39	Navigating social debt and its link with technical debt in large-scale agile software development projects.	2024	Saeeda <i>et al.</i>	[39]
PS40	Revealing social debt with the CAFFEA framework: An antidote to architectural debt.	2017	Martini and Bosch.	[40]
PS41	Beyond technical aspects: How do community smells influence the intensity of code smells?	2020	Palomba <i>et al.</i>	[41]
PS42	The Pandora’s box of social, process, and people debts in software engineering.	2022	Ahmad and Gustavsson.	[42]

Table 2: Primary studies

Id	Paper	Year	Author	Origin	Reference
PS43	Gender diversity and women in software teams: How do they affect community smells?	2019	Catolino <i>et al.</i>	PS11	[43]
PS44	What is social debt in software engineering.	2013	Tamburri <i>et al.</i>	PS24	[44]
PS45	Social debt in software engineering: insights from industry.	2015	Tamburri <i>et al.</i>	PS24	[45]

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